

On the origin of the Ryukyuan indicative

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Amongst many Ryukyuan languages is a peculiar suffix of various forms. Termed variously “indicative”, “realis” or “conclusive” marker, its form and function is oftentimes compared to its apparent morphological counterpart in Japanese, the *Shuushikei* (終止形) or conclusive form. However, when examined more in depth, various issues begin appearing that puts into question how valid this comparison is diachronically. This paper will examine the forms, functions and origins of this indicative suffix, evaluating the two competing hypotheses concerning its etymology.

1. Form and function

The indicative, languages with the potential exception of Old Okinawa (See Section 3), is attested in all Ryukyuan. Formally, Ryukyuan languages generally point towards some sort of simplex nasal, especially a labial nasal (Table 1). Based on these the scattered reflexes, various authors have reconstructed the indicative in Proto-Ryukyuan as **-mu* (Thorpe 1983, Uchima 1984).

Morphologically, the indicative can attach onto many suffixes, though, which combinations are permitted does vary by language. It is always found after the Present (all languages) but also to varying degrees after the Past (Tokunoshima, Shuri, etc.) and Negative (Yonaguni, etc.). Nonetheless, the indicative in general is an exclusively finite affix, being noticeably absent after most non-finite suffixes.

Functionally, this is another aspect in which the precise details vary by language but in general, a few broad trends can be drawn. One main restriction/tendency is that the indicative often exhibits does not co-occur with the focus particle **=do*. For much of Ryukyuan, the indicative is inexplicably tied to the conclusive form of the verb. However, there are two major exceptions: Amami in the North and Miyako in the South.

In Amami, forms with the indicative exist in parallel to forms without. Yoron for instance has an opposition between Indicative *-jun* vs Indicative-less *-jui*. Here, the indicative is described as being used for a) when the intentions of the agent is recognised, b) a non-habitual, exception action or c) a strongly subjective judgement (Machi 2016).

As for Miyako, the indicative serves a similar function. In Irabu Miyako, Shimoji (2008) describes it as marking “predicate focus” and expressing “(a) speaker’s perceived certainty, and (b) high information value”.

		Declarative	Interrogative
Amami	Yuwan	$-N^1$	$-m(-i)$
	Asama	$-N^1$	$-m(-i)$
	Yoron	$-N$	$-mm(-i)$
Okinawa	Nakijin	$-N$	$-m(-i)$
	Shuri	$-N$	$-m(-i)$
.....			
Miyako	Ōgami	$-m$	
	Irabu	$-m$	
Yaeyama	Ishigaki	$-N$	
	Yonaguni	$-N$	

Table 1: Forms of the Indicative amongst Ryukyuan varieties (Interrogative morpheme in brackets)

Summarising the facts, it can be concluded that the indicative suffix has the following properties:

1. It has a proto-form $*-mu$.
2. It is finite.
3. It marks predicate focus and does not co-occur with the argument focus marker $*=do$.

2. Dual origins

Due to sharing the restriction of having the Indicative cooccur with the focus particle, various authors have tried to link this suffix to the functional and syntactic Japanese counterpart, the Conclusive $*-u$ (Vovin 2020). However, many comparisons to the Japanese Conclusive have struggled with finding a suitable origin for the labial nasal element. Thorpe (1983) only comments that it is “probably an originally optional enclitic, possibly $*mu$ (Ry.) ‘Additive Focus’” and Karimata (2024) states simply that it “is thought to be similar to the suffix $-mu$ [presumably tentative $-(a)m-u$] that showed supposition or the speaker’s volition in Old Japanese”. Vovin (2020) rejects the

¹ These forms are functionally an attributive as well, but this seems to be an Amami unique innovation.

traditional auxiliary etymology and directly reconstructs a conclusive **-um* to Proto-Japonic. However, this proposal is problematic in a few aspects (see Section 5).

Thus synthesising previous analysis, there exists apparently two major proposals concerning the etymology of the indicative: from tentative **-am-* and from the focus particle **=mu*. Between the two, the focus particle **=mu* appears to be the more likely etymology. For the first etymology, **=mu* would attach onto the conclusive for the verb. In Amami-Okinawa, where most finite forms form from auxiliary constructions², specifically from contractions of Infinitive **-i* + [Auxiliary], **=mu* would exclusively attach onto the main auxiliaries of **wor-i* “*exist-ss*” and **ar-i* “*exist-ss*”. In Shuri, both auxiliaries, when existing in an independent form and when fused on as an auxiliary, have irregular stems: independent *wun* and *an* and auxiliary *-un* and *-an*³ (respectively from **wo-mu* and **a-mu*). Presumably some sort of elision would have had to have occurred to eliminate the syllable **ri*. Whilst normally the postulation of an irregular shift would weaken the argument, in this case, it seems that Proto-Ryukyuan was already actively eliding the **ri* in *r*-irregular verbs. As Thorpe (1983) points out, many Ryukyuan languages seem to evidence an irregular contracted converbial form of *r*-irregular verb: **wote* instead of expected **woQte~worite*. In Amami-Okinawa, we find Urasoe *wuti* for *wur-* (compare *tuQti* for *tur-*) (Nakamoto 1992) or Naha with *wuti* (but *tuQti*) (Uchima & Arakaki 2000). In Sakishima, examples include past conjugations in Irabu: *utam* for *ur-* (compare *turtam* for *tur-*) or in Ōgami: *utam* for *ur-* (compare *tuutam* for *tur-*).

By contrast, the proposal of that derives the indicative the tentative **-am-* is somewhat problematic. Thorpe (1983) does note some Ryukyuan languages irregularly truncate **ra* in the negative (**woranu*) and conditional (**woraba*) forms of auxiliary **wor-* to **wonu* and **woba*. However, all such noted forms appear to be exclusively attested in Sakishima, unlike the pan-Ryukyuan nature of elided **ri* in **womu* and **amu*. Amami-Okinawa typically reflects the expected full forms **woranu* and **woraba*.

Expanding beyond Ryukyuan, both forms are attested in the Japanese branch: **-am-u* for the tentative and a particle **-mā* attaching after the sentence final form to form an exclamative (Vovin 2020). At first glance, ignoring the issues concerning elision of *ra*, the tentative appears a more perfect match phonetically to Ryukyuan **-mu*⁴. Yet, this is only if we do not account that the focus particle **=mu* was also irregularly raised in Ryukyuan. As such, the truth of the reality is that neither reigns stronger on this front. Semantically, it appears that the tentative is a closer match,

² Whilst an auxiliary origin for Amami-Okinawa finite forms is mostly accepted as consensus, whether this can be cross applied onto Sakishima is controversial. Pellard (2010) makes a case that this process also underlines finite forms in Miyako which I am inclined to agree with. In the context of this examination however, we will side-step this debate as it does not concern the central ideas as **-mu* operates independently of those which occurs before it.

³ It is also to be noted that the direct Japanese cognate to the Ryukyuan forms also underwent irregular truncation to Past tense *-Ta* < **-te ar*

⁴ Irregular post-nasal raising is also found in the Proto-Ryukyuan lexeme **monu* < Proto-Japonic **māna*

marking Intention, Suggestion and Supposition as opposed to the exclamative which only marks Exclamation (Vovin 2020). In spite of this, a semantic shift from an exclamative > supposition/volitional > predicate focus is not too conceptually far-fetched.

One point that is to be noted concerns Ryukyuan's apparent semantic equivalent to Japanese **-am-*: the suffix **-a* (Shuri *'jum-a* "read-vol, Let's read"). Thorpe (1983) suggests that this suffix originates as "a conditional" and seems to reject its cognacy to Japanese **-am-u*. Indeed, the expected cognate form to Japanese **-am-u* in Ryukyuan would be forms in *-an*. Kikai and other Amami localities do show a suffix in *-oo* (< **-au?*) which Thorpe suggests is a recent loan from Japanese. I am inclined to agree with this assessment. However, concerning Thorpe's overall point, I believe instead that there is evidence to suggest that the Ryukyuan volition **-a* is indeed a cognate to Japanese **-am-u* and from hence its status as being the cognate/origin of the indicative should be questioned.

3. Evidence for the tentative

One line of evidence that has been missing thus far from discussions is the interpretation of Old and Classical Okinawan, our only substantial pre-modern attestations of a Ryukyuan language.

The indicative is barely attested in Old Okinawan with only one potential example I am aware of: the verb form おとちやむ <*o to ti ya mu*> *ʌtʰucʰyam* "lost" (OS 20.#1366) < **otos-i-te a(r-i)-mu* "fall- INF-CVB exist-SS-IND". Assuming the derivation is correct, this singular attestation would seem to evidence that the elision of **rV* had already occurred by the Old Okinawan period.

By contrast, the volition is way more robustly attested in the *Omoro Sōshi* in two forms: as either *-a*, as per Ryukyuan cognates, or as *-an*, as the expected cognate to **-am-u*⁵ (Serafim & Shinzato 2020). There seems to be no apparent semantic nor syntactic distinction between the two forms, suggesting they are variants of one another. Based on this variation, it seems that *-an* was being irregularly truncated during Old Okinawan, or even possibly from earlier periods. The reason for this truncation is readily apparent; to avoid homophony with the negative suffix *-an* (< **-an-u*).

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, by examining previous proposals concerning the origins of the indicative suffix in Ryukyuan, it is suggested here that the mostly likely origin for the Ryukyuan indicative comes from a particle **=mu* used after the conclusive form of verbs, cognate to an exclamative in Japanese. Specifically, in Amami-Okinawa at least, it originates from an auxiliary formation of the form **-i wor-i-mu* with an irregular truncation of syllable **ri*. It is possible this particle is the focus particle **=mu* but more research may be needed.

⁵ One piece of evidence that further supports the cognacy of *-an* to Japanese **-am-* is the existence of the evidential form *-am-i* (**-am-e*) in Old Okinawan, revealing the underlying form of the suffix handily as *|-am-|*. Additionally, I have also been informed to that this form also survives in the Classical and Modern Okinawan assertative *-sa(ra)mi* < **=su ar-am-e* "=_{FP} exist-TENT-EVD"

Additionally, any relation between the Ryukyuan indicative and the Japanese tentative *-am- is rejected here. Instead, I propose here that the Ryukyuan tentative *-a is the true cognate to the Japanese tentative.

5. Addendum: On Vovin's reconstruction of conclusive *-um

Vovin (2020) reconstructs Proto-Japonic *-um, segmenting forms such as Okinawan *kachun* into *kak-j-un*. Furthermore, he also rejects the traditional etymology of the Ryukyuan indicative forms as being from *-i wo-mu in favour of *-i-um.

There are several problems with this hypothesis. First, as has been discussed, Miyako varieties allow for forms without the final -m: Ōgami *kaks*, Karimata, Ikema, Nagahama, Nakachi *kafu* and Hirara, Shiokawa *kakɿ* (Pellard 2009). This in on itself strongly suggests that what Vovin sees as monomorphemic is in fact complex in origin, composed of *-ɿ “non-past” and *-m “IND”.

Even ignoring Vovin's erroneous segmentation, his assessment and rejection of the traditional etymology hinges itself on a few assumptions, none of which are particularly valid. First, he assumes the Shuri form *wun* (< *wu-i-um < *wor-i-um) itself incorporates his putative suffix *-um. Yet, his proposed list of sound changes is untenable. According to his evolution, the expected evolution of other regular *r*-verbs such as *tor- “to grab” should have been: *tor-i-um > tu-i-um > *tun. However, the attested Shuri form is *tujun* instead. Thus, his argument over phonetic circularity does not hold and we are indeed dealing with an irregular form.

Additionally, Vovin's formation of *wor-i-um as the proposed auxiliary construction is also somewhat questionable. Vovin claims Ryukyuan “does not offer any evidence for the stative / active distinction between -i and -u found in Western Old Japanese.” This is incorrect. A unique stative Conclusive marker is attested in abundance in Ryukyuan. In Old Okinawan, we find forms such as in たちより <ta ti yo ri> t^hac^oyuryi (OS 11.#564) “standing” < *tat-i-wor-i “stand-INF-PRG-SS”; in Amami, it is reflected in derivations from *-i wor-i: Yuwan -jui < *-juri < *-i wor-i. As such, especially accounting for the evidence from modern varieties, we should expect any construction involving this auxiliary to take the form *wor-i, not *wor-i-um with an unexpected conclusive.

Not only so, but Vovin also assumed the *u* in his reconstructed suffix is the origin of the thematic ⁱu in Amami-Okinawa. This is likely incorrect as well. Thematic ⁱu more likely originates not from any putative indicative suffix in *-um, but rather from the auxiliary verb *wor- itself. This is readily evident in other conjugated forms of Shuri with thematic ⁱu- such as the “Second past” extension -jut- < *-i wor-i-t(e)- “-INF exist-INF-CVB-” where the appearance of a conclusive in this auxiliary construction would certainly be surprising.

Overall, Vovin's reconstruction of a Proto-Japonic suffix *-um does not inspire significant confidence, suffering from disagreements with both established wisdom and the actual data on the

group. As such, I reject this reconstruction and treat the *Shuushikei* and the Indicative as separate morphemes in this paper.

Abbreviations

CVB	Converb	OS	<i>Omoro Sōshi</i>
EVD	Evidential	PRG	Progressive
FP	Focus particle	SS	Conclusive/ <i>Shuushikei</i>
IND	Indicative	TENT	Tentative
INF	Infinitive	VOL	Volitional

References

Karimata, S. (2024). Ryukyuan languages: A grammar overview. Handbook of the Ryukyuan Languages.

Leveque, D. (2021). Grammaire de l'asama [Doctoral thesis, Institut National des Langues et Civilisations Orientales].

Machi, H. (2016). Yoron hōgen no bunnō [Grammar of the Yoron dialect]. Yoron hōgen · Okinoerabu hōgen chōsa kenkyūshū [Investigation into the Yoron · Okinoerabu dialects], 63-74.

Nakasone, S. (1983) Okinawa Nakijin Hoogen Jiten [A dictionary of the dialect of Nakijin, Okinawa]. Tokyo: Kadokawa.

Niinaga, Y. (2014). A grammar of Yuwan [Doctoral thesis, University of Tokyo].

Pellard, T. (2009). Ōgami: éléments de description d'un parler du Sud des Ryukyu [Doctoral thesis, École des Hautes Études en Sciences Sociales].

Pellard, T. (2010). Review of "A Linguistic History of the Forgotten Islands: A reconstruction of the protolanguage of the Southern Ryukyus" , by John Bentley. *Diachronica*, 27(1), 170-176.

Shimoji, M. (2008). A Grammar of Irabu, a Southern Ryukyuan Language [Doctora thesis, Australian National University].

Thorpe, M. (1983). Ryūkyūan Language History [Doctoral thesis, University of Southern California].

Uchima, C.. (1984). Ryūkyū hōgen bunnō no kenkyū [Research in the Grammar of Ryukyuan Dialects]. Tokyo: Kasama Shoin.

Uchima, C., & Arakaki, K. (2000). Okinawa hokubu · nanbu hōgen no kisetu teki kenkyū [A description of dialects from the North and South of Okinawa]. Kazama Shobo.

Urabe, Y. (2022). Nan-ryūkyū Yaeyama-go Ishigaki-jima Shiraho hōgen no kisetu kenkyū [A description of the dialect of Shiraho, Ishigaki island, Southern Ryukyus] [Doctoral thesis, Kyushu University].

Vovin, A. (2020). A Descriptive and Comparative Grammar of Western Old Japanese (2nd ed.). Brill.

Yamada M., Pellard T., Shimoji M. (2016). Dunan grammar (Yonaguni Ryukyuan). Heinrich, Patrick; Miyara, Shinsho; Shimoji, Michinori. Handbook of the Ryukyuan languages: History, structure, and use, De Gruyter Mouton, pp.449–478, 2015, 978-1-61451-161-8. <10.1515/9781614511151.449>. <hal-01289268>